

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

IMPROVING THE MONITORING AND MANAGEMENT OF CONSTIPATION IN
PATIENTS TAKING ANTIPSYCHOTICS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Arnold Franco

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Kate Bayhan, DNP, RN, CCRN, Team Leader
Stephanie Vaughn, PhD, RN, CRRN, FAHA, FARN, Team Member

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Author Note

Arnold Franco - <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-4927-5902>
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ABSTRACT

Patients taking antipsychotic medications are at increased risk of constipation. Improved monitoring and management of constipation in patients taking antipsychotics could prevent adverse events and outcomes such as paralytic ileus, small bowel obstruction, and death. Thus, early recognition of constipation is vital in the routine surveillance of symptoms. The purpose of this evidence-based project is to develop and implement a care bundle of interventions that incorporates the Bristol Stool Form Scale (BSFS), educational modules for staff, and the creation of an electronic health record (EHR) alert system for the early detection and management of constipation in adult patients taking antipsychotics. Using the Iowa Model as the supporting framework, this care bundle was designed to help decrease the incidence of severe constipation and prevent serious complications and patient hospitalizations due to unresolved constipation. Data collection of participants' pretest and post-test scores and retrospective EHR review were used to evaluate project outcomes. A two-tailed paired samples t-test was conducted to examine whether the mean difference between pretest and post-test scores was statistically significant. A chi-square test of independence was also employed to determine if participant answers, and pre/post-test questions were related. Results of the two-tailed paired samples t-test and Chi-square test results were significant based on an alpha value of $<.05$ following data analysis. The findings imply increased participants' knowledge and understanding of BSFS and its clinical implication. Implementing a care bundle that included the BSFS screening tool, educational module, and EHR alert system improved patient care outcomes.

Keywords: constipation, antipsychotic medications, systematic review, fecal impaction, screening, prevention, and management.

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Background

Patients with psychiatric disorders undergo various experiences due to their condition, and antipsychotic medications' side effects can exacerbate these experiences. Constipation is common in patients with psychiatric disorders, with approximately 36.3% of patients with schizophrenia and 57.7% of those with depression reporting this symptom over a two-year period (Jessurum et al., 2016). Patients who routinely take antipsychotic medications experience a high prevalence of constipation that is often severe, and they require medical intervention (De Hert et al., 2011b; Chang & Chen, 2021). A literature review conducted by De Hert et al. (2011a) found that 12% to 22% of serious adverse events associated with constipation had fatal outcomes. In 2009, the total costs of constipation drugs exceeded \$40,000 in one hospital study (De Hert et al., 2011a). As a comparison, the cost of medications used for constipation is 30% of the cost of slow-release injectable antipsychotics, 7% of the total cost of antipsychotic medications, and five times the amount spent on anticholinergic medications used for motor side effects (De Hert et al., 2011a). In addition to being costly, constipation related to antipsychotic use also has the potential to cause serious health problems among the vulnerable group.

Setting the Stage

Statement of the Problem

This project addresses the need for enhanced early detection and management of constipation among patients using antipsychotic medications in an inpatient psychiatric setting. Clinical staff can easily overlook constipation as a symptom when treating patients taking antipsychotics. The tendency to overlook this symptom is often attributed to challenges in self-care and health awareness, as well as higher pain thresholds or higher tolerance for discomfort in patients with psychiatric disorders. Thus, early recognition of constipation is vital in the routine

surveillance of symptoms, which then assists in optimizing treatment (Sarangi et al., 2021). Early detection and treatment of symptoms related to constipation could prevent adverse events and negative outcomes such as paralytic ileus, small bowel obstruction, and death (De Hert et al., 2011b; Xu et al., 2021).

Although constipation is underreported and not assessed systematically, it is a common side effect of many antipsychotic agents (De Hert et al., 2011, Xu et al., 2021). Fifty percent of patients receiving antipsychotic treatment reported being constipated (Xu et al., 2021).

Constipation has an incidence rate of 15 per 100 persons per year in patients with severe psychiatric disorders (Jessurun et al., 2016). Constipation can impact a psychiatric patient's quality of life by triggering anal fissures, hemorrhoids, and infection that lead to intestinal obstruction and ischemic bowel disease, sometimes progressing to septicemia, aspiration pneumonia, and intestinal perforation in severe cases (Xu et al., 2021).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this evidence-based practice (EBP) project is to develop a care bundle of interventions that incorporates the implementation of the BSFS (Appendix A), educational modules for staff, and the creation of an EHR alert system for early detection and management of constipation in adult patients taking antipsychotic medications. This care bundle of interventions is designed to improve the facility's monitoring and management of constipation and prevent serious complications and patient hospitalizations due to unresolved constipation.

Supporting Framework

EBP models provide a systematic approach to identifying and addressing clinical problems based on the most recent literature (Brown, 2014). Gawlinski and Rutledge (2008) reported that using an EBP model for quality improvement enables nurse researchers to focus

resources on a systematic approach. For this DNP project, the Iowa Model-Revised will be used to guide the implementation of a new workflow that incorporates the BSFS for early detection and management of constipation in adult patients taking antipsychotic medications in a 140-bed psychiatric facility located in Southern California.

The Iowa Model

The Iowa Model of Research-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care was created in 1994 and implemented at the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics (Titler et al., 2001). The model provides a systematic structure for nurses and other healthcare providers to apply research findings into clinical practice to improve patient outcomes. Nurses consider it intuitively understandable and easy to use (Brown, 2014; Titler et al., 2001). Additionally, the model is frequently used in academic and healthcare settings to address academic and clinical problems (Brown, 2014). According to Titler et al. (2001), the model was renamed due to a shift from a “Research-Based Practice” to an “Evidence-Based Practice” model.

The Iowa Model-Revised

Several revisions were made to the 1994 model based on user feedback, analysis of EBP literature, and emerging social and environmental factors in the healthcare market (Titler et al., 2001). Changes in the healthcare system, such as the emergence of implementation science and customer-focused initiatives, prompted further reevaluation, revision, and validation of the model (Iowa Model Collaborative et al., 2017). These revisions were designed to address the sustainability of EBP, an implementation by interdisciplinary teams, and patient-centered care for clinicians at all levels of practice. The Iowa Model’s current revision is named Iowa Model Revised: Evidenced-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care (Appendix B).

Permission to reprint the Model's image and use it as the project framework was obtained from the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics (Appendix C).

The model has seven steps and three discussion points. The model starts with identifying the clinical "trigger" or clinical problem. Once the clinical problem is identified, a statement of the problem must be developed. The model integrates decision points with evaluative feedback loops to guide the nurse in implementing practice changes. The model also includes the formation of an interprofessional team, the review, appraisal, and synthesis of the research evidence, the design and pilot implementation of changes, ongoing evaluation, integration, and the sustainment of practice changes, and dissemination of the outcomes (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017).

Integration of Iowa Model-Revised into the Scholarly Project

The following section describes the use of the model to guide this DNP project, which focused on implementing a care bundle of interventions that incorporated the use of the BSFS for early detection and management of constipation in adult patients taking antipsychotic medications in a 140-bed acute psychiatric facility located in Southern California.

Identify Triggering Issues and Stating the Question

According to the Model, all practice change initiatives should begin with identifying a clinical trigger. The clinical trigger for this DNP project is the increased hospitalization of patients, during the fourth quarter of 2021 and second quarter of 2022, for the treatment and management of fecal impaction. One incident resulted in a patient requiring surgical intervention to resolve the subsequent bowel obstruction. The patient stayed two months in the hospital in the sub-acute unit due to complications from the surgery. The second patient hospitalized during the

second quarter of 2022 expired a few days after hospital admission due to complications from fecal impaction.

The next step in the model is forming the question and purpose. Once the clinical question has been finalized, the model guides the user to the first decision point, determining whether the problem is a priority for the institution. Prioritizing a topic is important because organizational buy-in is essential to support the proposed work (Brown, 2014). For this DNP project, patient constipation resulting in fecal impaction has been determined as a priority based on the facility's principles and strategic plans. In addition, the project will promote patient safety, improve disease outcomes by reducing symptom burden, and align with cost-saving strategies. According to the model, formally stating the purpose enables a more focused approach to synthesizing the body of evidence and better informs the subsequent decision points. Once the clinical problem is identified as a priority to the facility, the next step is forming a team of members who will help develop, evaluate, and implement the EBP change. The team then collaborates and decides on the remaining steps of the model.

Forming a Team

According to Brown (2014), the type of issue identified determines the team's composition. It is important that the team includes interdisciplinary stakeholders who are team players outside of nursing and are invested in the project development, such as information technology, accounting, and training and development staff (Titler et al., 2001). For this DNP project, the team consisted of the Director of Nursing (DON), the minimum data set (MDS) coordinator, charge nurses from the pilot unit, and the Staff Developer. The project lead (PL) also recruited and instituted a bowel management champion from the pilot unit who monitored the implementation and reported potential problems to the team lead. According to the model,

the team's makeup may evolve; however, no additional team members were added following the initial implementation of this project.

Assemble, Appraise, and Synthesize the Body of Evidence

After forming the project team, the next step of the model is to conduct a systematic search of relevant literature. Selected articles were selected and critically appraised for quality, consistency of evidence, and risks involved in implementing the practice change. The literature review by the PL showed evidence to support the implementation of the proposed EBP change intended for this pilot project.

Design and Pilot the Practice Change

The model states that before integrating a facility-wide implementation of the EBP change, the team must design and pilot-test the proposed practice change to ensure the change is feasible and will result in improved outcomes. This step includes engaging patients and verifying their preferences, considering resources, constraints, and approval, developing the localized protocol, creating an evaluation plan, collecting baseline data, developing an implementation plan, preparing necessary materials, and educating clinicians.

Participants and patients were essential stakeholders in this project. The PL reviewed patient demographics, the outcomes of constipation management, and the doctor's medication orders through a retrospective chart review of the EHR. After considering patient information, the PL developed a protocol to integrate BSFS into the current monitoring workflow, a process to collect baseline and surveillance data, and an evaluation of data from the EHR review. The design for this pilot project will be discussed further in the Methods section.

Integrate and Sustain the Practice Change

According to the model, integrating and sustaining a practice change can be difficult. The main suggestion for sustaining change is to highlight the project results and tie them into quality improvement methods. Therefore, the team must identify and engage key nursing personnel as champions to help integrate and sustain the hospital-wide practice change. Including this component will create relationships and coordination within hospital administration. This way, the team can promote much-needed influences from senior leadership and stakeholders. To evaluate the efficacy of the practice change, the PL conducted regular EHR audits and monitored the proper use of the tool and laxatives. The unit champion also provided feedback on any issues related to the project to the PL for review and troubleshooting. For this project, the measures of successful EBP change will include a staff increase in knowledge of the tool used for early detection of constipation, an appropriate response to the EHR alert system, a decrease in the incidence of fecal impaction per quarter, and decreased hospitalizations related to unresolved constipation for four months.

Disseminate Results

The last step in the model is disseminating the results of the practice change. The plan for dissemination will include publishing the project results in the facility newsletter, recommending the update of the facility's policy and procedures to integrate hospital-wide practice change, and conducting training sessions and poster presentations facility-wide. Additionally, the team will discuss with stakeholders the extension of this EBP change to a sister facility.

Review of Literature

Overview

A comprehensive literature search was conducted to identify and retrieve publications relevant to constipation screening and management in adult patients taking antipsychotic medications. The searched electronic databases included PubMed, CINAHL, Scotus, and Google Scholar. Key search terms and combinations included “constipation,” “antipsychotic medications,” “systematic review,” “fecal impaction,” and “screening, prevention, and management.” The search was limited to peer-reviewed journals written in English and published between 2016 and 2022. The search resulted in 1,974 studies. A review of these articles by title or abstract for relevance to the topic and removing duplicate articles left 61 articles. A review of the 61 articles was conducted to remove articles that did not include constipation as a primary outcome measure, patients taking antipsychotic medications in outpatient settings, constipation in children, and constipation due to irritable bowel syndrome, which left 18 articles for the literature review. A manual review of the reference section of the 18 articles identified two additional articles, making 24 the total number of articles used in the literature review. The selected articles comprised observational studies, retrospective cohort studies, and one case study. One randomized control trial by Lewis and Heaton (1997) was also obtained, which evaluated the validity of the BSFS. Additionally, one systematic review and meta-analysis were found, which reviewed research on antipsychotic-induced constipation.

This project aims to develop and implement a care bundle of interventions that features the implementation of the BSFS to improve early detection and management of constipation in a psychiatric care setting and to prevent the burden of hospitalization due to fecal impaction. To achieve this aim, the PL explored the literature and identified four possible key categories of

interest: antipsychotic-induced constipation (AIC), antipsychotics with a high propensity to induce constipation, approaches to screening and treatment of AIC, and tools for early detection and management AIC.

Antipsychotic-Induced Constipation

Antipsychotic medications are the cornerstone in treating schizophrenia and other psychiatric disorders. While antipsychotic drugs benefit patients in a psychiatric setting (Xu et al., 2021), their use is associated with adverse effects that can affect patients' physical and psychological well-being, such as constipation. Antipsychotic medications such as trifluoperazine, loxapine, fluphenazine, quetiapine, olanzapine, clozapine, and paliperidone have a high risk of inducing constipation (Xu et al., 2021). In a retrospective cohort study, Chen and Hsieh (2018) found that the incidence of constipation in schizophrenia treated with antipsychotics was 42.5 cases per 1000 persons per year (95% CI: 41.1–44.0). Patients on a combination of typical and atypical antipsychotics had the highest prevalence of constipation, at 41.7% (Xu et al., 2021). Yet, AIC continues to receive less attention and remains largely unrecognized (De Hert et al., 2011; Nakamura et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2021).

In patients with psychiatric disorders, constipation can be attributed to many risk factors, including a sedentary lifestyle, obesity, reduced fiber intake, and dehydration (De Hert et al., 2011; Shirazi et al., 2016; Nakamura et al., 2021). Other risk factors include gastrointestinal hypomotility (GIHM) and slow colonic transit time (CTT), which is defined as the amount of time ingested substances move through the colon (Xu et al., 2021, Chen & Hsieh, 2018). Every-Palmer et al. (2017) reported that GIHM happens in 50% to 80% of patients prescribed clozapine. The pathogenesis of antipsychotic-induced GIHM can be linked to the peripheral anticholinergic activity that slows down peristalsis (De Hert et al., 2011). The risk of GIHM is

higher when antipsychotic medications are combined with other anticholinergic medications and can cause potentially life-threatening consequences (Every-Palmer et al., 2017; Shirazi et al., 2016; Xu et al., 2021). In a 2020 case study, Logre et al. concluded that chronic constipation with fecal impaction is a common complication in patients taking antipsychotic medications. Severe fecal impaction can lead to adverse events and even death. Unfortunately, few studies have focused on mortality rates related to AIC.

Antipsychotics With High Propensity to Induce Constipation

Clozapine-Induced Constipation

Clozapine-induced constipation (CIC) affects up to 80% of users due to GI hypomotility; however, the condition is less frequently explored (Every-Palmer et al., 2020). Clozapine is a second-generation antipsychotic medication approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for treatment-resistant schizophrenia. According to Shirazi et al. (2016), patients receiving clozapine are three times more likely to have constipation than those treated with another antipsychotic. A systematic review conducted by Palmer et al. (2017) established that clozapine slows down gastrointestinal motility, leading to constipation, with approximately 60% of patients receiving clozapine reporting that they experienced constipation. Xu et al. (2021) found that the case-fatality rate for clozapine-induced GIHM was 15% to 27.5%. Despite the higher mortality rate, AIC remains underrecognized (Chen & Hsieh, 2018; De Hert et al., 2011; Shirazi et al., 2016). On January 28, 2020, the FDA released enhanced warnings about the risk of serious and sometimes fatal complications associated with constipation caused by clozapine (Nakamura et al., 2021). This heightened warning may help increase healthcare providers' awareness of this problem and prompt them to seek additional means to prevent and treat AIC.

Other Antipsychotics Inducing Constipation

De Hert et al. (2011) conducted a systematic review that compared second-generation antipsychotics to other antipsychotics that induce constipation due to their anticholinergic activity. The study indicated that quetiapine had increased anticholinergic side effects (31%) compared to olanzapine (24%), risperidone (25%), or ziprasidone (20%). Chen and Hsieh (2018) substantiated that quetiapine has a relatively high risk of inducing anticholinergic side effects, leading to constipation. Conversely, Rodríguez-Ramallo et al. (2021) concluded that there was a lack of studies testing the relationship between the anticholinergic effects and constipation. There is a need for higher quality studies that include analysis of confounding factors like non-pharmacological causes of constipation.

Approaches to Screening and Evaluation of AIC

Every-Palmer et al. (2020) conducted a diagnostic accuracy study on constipation screening in patients taking clozapine. The researchers examined the reliability of self-reported constipation and the Rome screening criteria compared with the referenced standard of gastrointestinal motility studies. The findings indicated that following 30 motility tests, constipation screening by self-reporting had inferior diagnostic properties in the inpatient group, which prompted the researchers to terminate the study. Only 26% of the participants self-reported constipation, with a sensitivity of 18% (95% CI: 5–40%), even though 73% of participants had confirmed clozapine-induced gastrointestinal hypomotility (CIGH) on motility testing. In other words, the gastrointestinal X-rays showed constipation even though the patients reported not being constipated.

Constipation self-reporting was identified as a poor measure of constipation in the inpatient group taking antipsychotics and a poor predictor of objective hypomotility (Every-Palmer et al., 2017; Every-Palmer et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2021). Therefore, under-reporting of

constipation can ensue in the psychiatric inpatient population. Attard et al. (2019) and Xu et al. (2021) suggested that underreporting is due to cognitive deficit, decreased pain threshold or sensation, symptoms of schizophrenia, reduced ability to communicate, and decreased symptom awareness. Because self-reporting is a poor measure of AIC, it is recommended that clinical staff consistently monitor, screen, and engage in preventative strategies for early detection of constipation (De Hert et al., 2011b; Logre et al., 2020; Nakamura et al., 2021; Every-Palmer et al., 2021; Shirazi et al., 2016; Xu et al., 2021). Chen and Hsieh (2018) affirmed that patients taking antipsychotics like high-potency first-generation antipsychotics (FGA), clozapine, or quetiapine should undergo proper assessment and intervention to reduce the disease burden and life-threatening outcomes of treatment. In addition, Attard et al. (2019) recommended that there needs to be a clear delineation of risk identified in prescribing guidelines, regulatory agencies, and manufacturers' information regarding CIGH. Constipation in patients taking clozapine should be prevented with prophylactic laxatives rather than treated only when it is clinically identified (Attard et al., 2019; Palmer et al., 2021).

Prophylactic Laxatives in Patients Taking Antipsychotic Medications

To date, limited randomized clinical trials (RCT) study the effect of treatment protocols on AIC. Palmer et al. (2017) concluded that no quality trial-based evidence was available to provide clinicians and patients guidance in the pharmacological treatment of AIC. In addition, methodologically rigorous RCTs are needed to evaluate interventions for treating AIC. In their systematic review, Palmer et al. (2017) identified two relevant studies in the Chinese literature, but none were identified in the Western literature on treating AIC. Therefore, a gap exists in the study of prevention and treatment protocols for this patient population.

Because constipation screening had poor diagnostic properties, Palmer et al. (2020) suggested prophylactic laxatives for patients taking clozapine. Several researchers concluded that early detection is crucial in preventing severe outcomes from AIC, such as small bowel obstruction, ileus, and fecal impaction (Attard et al., 2019; Every-Palmer et al., 2017; Logre et al., 2020; Nakamura & Nagamine, 2021; Patel et al., 2021; Shirazi et al., 2016; Xu et al., 2021). In addition, the researchers supported the liberal use of laxatives in patients taking clozapine. However, caution was given in using bulk-forming, fiber-based laxatives for slow-transit constipation-induced antipsychotics. These types of laxatives are ineffective against constipation secondary to the anticholinergic effects of the drugs (Patel et al., 2021).

Adequate patient education on maintaining good hydration, increasing dietary fiber intake, and performing regular exercise can also help prevent constipation (De Hert et al., 2011; Leung et al., 2011; Patel et al., 2021; Shirazi et al., 2016; Thompson, 2020). Xu et al. (2021) concluded that strict monitoring and evaluation of constipation, timely use of anti-constipation drugs, and avoiding the overuse of antipsychotics concomitant with other anticholinergic drugs are all effective in preventing severe or fatal gastrointestinal complications from the use of antipsychotics. Based on the study findings in treating CIGH and constipation called Porirua Protocol, Every-Palmer et al. (2020) and Xu et al. (2021) recommended using docusate and senna augmented by macrogol appeared effective in reducing CTT in clozapine-induced constipation.

Tools for Early Detection and Management of AIC

The Bristol Stool Form Scale

Xu et al. (2021) recommended that weekly constipation screening and continuous long-term monitoring are paramount to prevent severe constipation. Thompson (2020) posited that

using validated tools like the Bristol Stool Form Scale (BSFS) by Lewis and Heaton (1997) could help nurses in assessing the bowel function of patients. The BSFS tool can also provide information on stool appearance and detect constipation symptoms earlier (Lewis & Heaton, 1997). Chumpitazi et al. (2016) studied the reliability of BSFS and concluded that when used to rate individual stool types by raters, the BSFS has high interrater reliability. For this evidence-based practice project, the BSFS will be used and incorporated into the pilot unit workflow and EHR to assist clinical staff in the early detection, screening, and management of constipation.

Hynes et al. (2015) developed the Glasgow Antipsychotic Side-Effects Scale for Clozapine (GASS-C), a 19-item rating scale that assesses the side effects associated with the use of clozapine such as weight gain, sedation, hypersalivation, constipation, tremors, and sexual dysfunction. However, this scale was administered only to an outpatient population who were well-established with clozapine therapy. Therefore, the scale was not generalizable in an acute inpatient care setting. Shirazi et al. (2016) proposed that the BSFS tool be widely used to monitor stool frequency and consistency and should be implemented into protocols for monitoring constipation when initiating clozapine treatment. The BSFS was suggested to be a useful tool in improving monitoring further constipation after treatment of CIGH in patients taking clozapine (Attard et al., 2019).

Summary

The use of antipsychotics has many benefits in the treatment of psychiatric disorders. However, these drugs also have various adverse effects that increase the risk to patient safety. Constipation is one such adverse effect that has been identified with severe consequences if left unrecognized and untreated. During the past two decades, few RCTs have examined the prevention and management of constipation and its severe sequelae in patients taking

antipsychotic medications in a psychiatric inpatient setting other than CIC. Evidence suggests that this vulnerable population suffers the burden of AIC and is at risk of severe consequences due to patients' lack of reliable self-reporting of constipation and the lack of a structured process for early identification and management of AIC. The need for early detection and management is critical in the psychiatric inpatient population and is a common theme discussed in the literature.

A simple validated screening tool such as BSFS with consistent monitoring, adequate hydration, increased physical activities, and an appropriate diet was beneficial in tipping the benefit-risk scale towards preventing AIC and its sequelae. The use of common laxative prophylactics in patients taking clozapine and other antipsychotics with a high propensity for constipation is a low-risk intervention supported by evidence. There is evidence to support the practice change for this project. The team's next step is to develop the methods for implementing the project.

Methods

This EBP project incorporated a care bundle of interventions that included a BSFS screening tool for constipation, an educational module, and the creation of an EHR alert system for the early detection of constipation in patients taking antipsychotics. The project aim was to improve the monitoring and management of constipation and to prevent fecal impaction and its sequelae in the inpatient psychiatric setting.

Design

This evidence-based pilot project used the Iowa Model to guide the implementation of a care bundle of interventions. The Model has seven steps and three decision points described in the Framework section of this paper. These steps were followed to guide the creation, implementation, and assessment of this pilot project:

- A. Incorporated the BSFS into the pilot unit workflow.
- B. Developed and implemented an education module for employees with pre- and post-evaluation to increase participant knowledge of BSFS and its clinical implications.
- C. Coordinated with IT personnel to develop an EHR alert system to notify licensed staff and MD/NPs of patients' constipation side effects for early management.
- D. Collected and analyzed surveillance data to assess project impact and outcome.

Setting

The project took place in a 124-bed acute psychiatric facility in Southern California. The facility is in a low-income community with diverse ethnic minority groups. The facility is family owned and was established in 1974. It operates under a Skilled Nursing Facility license with the California Department of Public Health. In addition to psychiatric care and support, the facility provides post-acute, memory, and long-term care to more than 2,500 patients annually. The

psychiatric facility offers 24-hour licensed nursing staff serving its three psychiatric units (Unit 1, Unit 2, and Unit 3). The facility serves a diverse group of inpatient admissions consisting of Hispanic, Vietnamese Asian, Caucasian, African American, Middle Eastern, and Filipino patients. Most patients come from low-income families with no insurance coverage and speak and understand English. However, if needed, interpreters are available via staff translators and digital translation services. Some patients admitted are homeless and undocumented. The patient admission process begins with the County's Crisis Stabilization Unit. The patients are assessed by a County psychiatric team and placed on a legal hold before being referred for admission into the facility.

All psychiatric units in the facility cater to adult patients ranging from 18 to 65 years of age, with various acuity levels and varying types of psychiatric disorders. Patients in the pilot unit, Unit 2, have court-appointed public or private guardian conservatorships. Most patients admitted to the facility have no insurance and are supported and funded by the County Health Agency. The pilot unit has a 48-bed capacity and provides extended admission for psychiatric evaluation and support.

Patients' lengths of stay (LOS) in the pilot unit range from one to two years. All patients admitted to the facility and assessed by the psychiatric team receive at least one form of first-generation and second-generation psychotropic medication. Psychiatric and medical staff perform a history and physical assessment within 24 hours of admission. Consent for psychiatric treatment is provided voluntarily by patients or through the patient's legal guardian. All patients' medical treatments for chronic and acute conditions such as diabetes, hypertension, and constipation are ordered by an interdisciplinary staff composed of an MD and NPs.

Staff who work in all three units are comprised of Registered Nurses (RN), Licensed Vocational Nurses (LVN), Licensed Psychiatric Nurses (LPT), Mental Health Assistants (MHA), Social Workers (SW), Activity Therapists (AT), Psychiatrists, Psychologists, Nutritionists, and Housekeeping. The leadership team comprises a Medical Director, Program Director, Director of Nursing (DON), and Staff Development Officer/Staffing Coordinator. An RN House Supervisor performs the DON and Staffing Coordinator role on weekends. The facility contracts with a Medical Doctor (MD) and an NP group who provide the medical services on-site daily and via telephone consult during off hours.

Participants

The participants in this EBP project include level-of-care employees hired as full-time, part-time, and per diem RNs, LVNs, LPTs, and MHAs for the facility. These employees work or may be assigned to work in the pilot unit to provide 24-hour nursing care. There are three shifts for the nursing staff in Unit 2, the morning shift (AM), evening shift (PM), and night shift (NOC). The participants' age range is from 20-73 years old. Participants were hired before project implementation and worked directly with patients admitted to the pilot unit.

The pilot project was conducted in Unit 2 with plans for implementation in the other units upon project evaluation. Participants were recruited from the list of employees. Recruitment was enhanced using flyers, emails, text messages, and announcements posted in the OnShift Scheduling app, break rooms, and other common areas. Interested participants replied and indicated their preferred in-service time by replying to the OnShift Scheduling app notification. Attendance to the in-service hours was mandatory; however, participants could withdraw from being part of data collection at any time without penalty. Zero participants withdrew from the pilot project during its implementation.

Institutional Review Board Approval

The facility for this proposed EBP pilot project does not have an Institutional Review Board (IRB); therefore, the request for pilot project approval was submitted to IRB through California State University, Fullerton (Appendix D). Permission to conduct the pilot project was obtained from the facility's Medical Director (Appendix E). The nursing staff participating in the pilot project were provided with informed consent, explaining the purpose of the pilot project, their level of involvement, and the benefits of the pilot project to the patients served. The PL and Staff Developer worked together to obtain the signed informed consent (Appendix F) from the list of staff working throughout all shifts in the pilot unit.

To maintain confidentiality, the PL excluded all participant identifiers in collecting demographic information and all patient identifiers in surveillance data collection. Data were stored in the PL's locked workstation and on an encrypted USB drive.

Measures

The BSFS was used to screen for early detection of constipation in patients taking antipsychotics and residing in the pilot unit, Unit 2. The BSFS, also called Bristol Stool Chart, was developed as a clinical assessment tool in 1997(Lewis & Heaton, 1997). It includes seven types of stool forms and categories:

- A. Type 1 - Separate hard lumps, like nuts.
- B. Type 2 - Sausage-shaped but lumpy.
- C. Type 3 - Like a sausage or snake but with cracks on its surface.
- D. Type 4 - Like a sausage or snake, smooth and soft.
- E. Type 5 - Soft blobs with clear-cut edges.
- F. Type 6 - Fluffy pieces with ragged edges, a mushy stool.

G. Type 7 - Watery, no solid pieces.

The BSFS is easy to use, and the interpretation of the tool is simple to convey and understand. BSFS identifies the stool forms and types that indicate the likelihood of constipation.

The interpretation includes:

- A. Type 1-2 - Indicates constipation,
- B. Type 3-5 - Ideal stools as they are easier to pass, and
- C. Type 6-7 - May indicate diarrhea and urgency.

Currently, the facility defines constipation based only on BM frequency. For example, any three or fewer bowel movements reported in a week. All patients admitted to the facility are offered Senna S (osmotic laxative) daily if not contraindicated. In addition, a standing order of Milk of Magnesia (MOM) as needed (PRN) is added to patients' bowel management regimen if patients have no reported bowel movement (BM) for two days. If MOM PRN is ineffective, additional laxatives are considered according to the MD or NP's discretion. The treatment options range from magnesium citrate, Dulcolax, lactulose, suppository, and fleet enema.

Staff monitor patients' BMs daily through patient self-reporting during each eight-hour shift. The patients' responses are recorded in an Electronic Medical Record (EMR) system called PointClick Care (PCC). The staff records data regarding the stool size (small, medium, and large) and the time of defecation. If the patient has no BM for two consecutive days, MOM is offered according to the physician's order. The result of MOM administration is evaluated within 24 hours and recorded in PCC. The licensed nurse, like the RN, LVN, and LPT, reports all ineffective MOM PRN administered to MD or NP for further review and orders.

The current protocol lacks a valid screening tool to assess constipation, which can assist clinical decision-making. According to Every-Palmer et al. (2020), the Bristol Stool Form Scale

is clinically useful in determining stool form. Lewis and Heaton (1997) studied and confirmed the validity of the BSFS, which was determined to help assess treatment effectiveness. By adding the BSFS to the pilot unit's workflow and screening process for constipation, the staff integrated a valid screening tool that can be used to monitor changes in patients' GI functions (Lewis & Heaton, 1997). Permission from the Rome Foundation to use the BSFS as a measuring tool for this pilot project was obtained, and a standard license agreement was signed and approved accordingly (Appendix G).

Project Implementation

Guided by the Iowa Model, a trigger was first identified within the facility. For this DNP project, the clinical trigger was historic patient constipation resulting in fecal impaction and unexpected hospitalization. There were increased hospitalizations of patients related to fecal impaction during the fourth quarter of 2021 and the second quarter of 2022. One incident resulted in a patient requiring surgical intervention to resolve the subsequent bowel obstruction. The patient remained for two months in the hospital in the sub-acute unit due to complications from the surgery. During the second quarter of 2022, one patient was hospitalized and died due to complications from a small bowel obstruction. Therefore, this DNP project aimed to promote patient safety, decrease hospitalizations, and improve disease outcomes by reducing symptom burden.

To accomplish this outcome, the BSFS was integrated into the current BM monitoring protocol in the pilot unit, Unit 2. In addition to the staff recording the time and size of BM reported by patients, the staff documented the stool form and filled out the BSFS assessment tool in PCC on their work iPad devices. To initiate implementation, the PL worked with IT personnel to integrate the BSFS into the PCC's Assessment section and create an automatic alert feature

when types 1 and 2 are selected on the BSFS tool during the work shift. The PCC's Assessment section can accommodate and adopt different forms or tools for screening and evaluating the patient's medical and psychiatric conditions. The alert feature notifies staff and prescribers of any early indications of unresolved constipation requiring further assessment, treatment, and follow-up. Staff-recommended responses to the alert were as follows:

- A. Assessment of patient for acute abdomen by RN
- B. Review MD/NP orders for laxatives and administer them if indicated.
- C. Notify MD/NP of any abnormal findings, i.e., abdominal distention, pain, nausea/vomiting, hypoactive bowel sounds.
- D. If there were no abnormal findings, refer the patient for MD/NP consult for further evaluation and bowel regimen review.
- E. Update or initiate a health care plan for constipation as appropriate and policy.

When MD/NP received BSFS tool alert via staff reporting, consultation referral, and PCC review, MD/NP response included but was not limited to the following:

- A. Evaluation of patient and BM record
- B. Medication review that included bowel management regimen and adjustments to laxative orders, if indicated.
- C. Referral to other interdisciplinary team members (dietician, activity therapist, and psychiatrist)
- D. Other diagnostic tests, such as KUB, if indicated, particularly for patients taking clozapine and olanzapine.
- E. Evaluation and adjustment of antipsychotic medications, as indicated.
- F. GI specialist referral, if indicated.

Educational Module Development and Implementation

The PL developed the EM of the care bundle of interventions in coordination with the Staff Developer and the D.O.N. The EM was composed of a colored printed handout of the BSFS tool that was distributed to all participants and posted in the nurse's station and medication room windows. The EM also included a PPT presentation outlining the learning objectives, project purpose, and implementation. The PPT presentation discussed the BSFS tool and its integration into the PCC, the plans for data collection and analysis, and the project timeline. The EM featured a 10-item pretest and posttest questionnaire selected directly from educational information and the BSFS tool presented to the participants. This pre- and post-test questionnaire (Appendix H) was developed to measure nursing knowledge of BSFS and its implication and evaluate the EM's effectiveness.

The Staff Developer scheduled two mandatory EM in-service sessions on 11/29/22. The first session was presented at 7:00 am, and the second was conducted at 3:00 pm. Each session was one hour long and presented in the same training room. The paper pretest questionnaires were administered before the start of the PPT presentation. The paper post-test questionnaire was administered immediately following the PPT presentation. The PL and Staff Developer reviewed and tallied the pre-and post-test results on 11/30/22. Test scores were logged in an Excel file for data collection and analysis. Other data collected from the participants were demographic information, including race, gender, work title, and age. A descriptive analysis of participants' demographics is delineated in Appendix I, Table 1.

Data Collection and Management

A retrospective review of the PCC was conducted to determine the baseline number of patients with an active constipation diagnosis, requiring the use of MOM PRN for no BM for

two days or the use of additional laxatives due to ineffectiveness of MOM PRN, such as lactulose, suppository PRN five months before project implementation. In addition, pre-implementation data were collected on the number of KUBs ordered because of constipation concerns unresolved by conventional laxative treatment and the number of hospitalizations related to severe constipation or fecal impaction.

Following baseline data collection and initiation of BSFS implementation, surveillance data were collected weekly on the number of patients identified with constipation based on using the BSFS tool and patients who received MOM PRN. Surveillance data on using Lactulose PRN, Dulcolax suppository PRN, and the number of patients who received a KUB order were also collected. Patient hospitalization incidents related to severe constipation based on admission diagnosis were collected at the end of the pilot project implementation.

Data Analysis

Data from pre- and post-implementation were analyzed and compared using QI Macros and Intellectus Statistics electronic software. A QI Macros and control chart was used to monitor process performance and test the strength of the relationship between the implementation of care bundle of interventions for the early identification of constipation and indication of PRN laxatives. A two-tailed paired samples *t*-test was employed to examine whether the mean difference between pre- and post-test scores was significantly different from zero and to detect if there was a statistically significant increase in mean participant knowledge after receiving the EM in-service. A chi-square test of independence was conducted to examine whether participants' answers to pre-and post-test questions were independent. The significance level for both test analyses was set at $p < 0.05$. A descriptive analysis was conducted to examine the frequency of nominal and ordinal variables from participants' demographic data.

Results

Participant Analysis

Fifty-eight nursing staff participants signed the informed consent, received educational material, and attended the pre-implementation educational module in-service. Fifty-three (91%) participants completed both the pretest and posttest. Two participants had to leave the in-service after discussion and did not complete the posttest. Three participants in the 3:00 pm session arrived at the in-service late and did not complete the pretest. Subsequently, these five participants were excluded from the final pre-and post-test data collection and analysis. Ten RNs, nine LVNs, five LPTs, and 34 MHAs participated (Appendix J, Figure 1).

Pre- and Post-Test Analysis

A two-tailed paired samples t-test was conducted to examine whether the mean difference between Pre-Test Scores and Post-Test Scores significantly differed from zero. The result of the two-tailed paired samples t-test was significant based on an alpha value of .05, $t(52) = -10.31$, $p < .001$. There was a difference in the mean of pre-test scores, and the mean of post-test scores was significantly different from zero. The mean of the pretest scores was significantly lower than the mean of the post-test scores. This finding suggests an increase in the correct post-test scores after the EM presentation, as indicated by a p-value of $< .001$. The results are presented in Appendix I, Table 2. A bar plot of the means is presented in Appendix J, Figure 2 (Intellectus Statistics, 2022).

A Chi-square Test of Independence was conducted to examine whether participants' answers and pre-and post-test questionnaires were independent. There were two levels in participants' Answers: Correct and Incorrect. There were two levels in Questionnaire: Pretest and Post-test (Appendix I, Table 2).

The Chi-square test results were significant based on an alpha value of .05, $\chi^2(1) = 19.09$, $p < .001$, suggesting that there were statistically significant differences in responses between the pretest and the posttest. Appendix I, Table 3, presents the Chi-square test results (Intellectus Statistics, 2022).

Constipation Identification and Laxative Use

A retrospective EHR review was completed from July 1, 2022, to November 29, 2022, and from November 30, 2022, to March 14, 2023, post-implementation. Thirty-six weeks of data were collected on MOM PRN use, other laxatives used, and diagnostic KUB ordered. In addition, the number of patients identified with constipation based on laxative PRN was collected pre- and post-implementation (Appendix J, Figure 3).

Appendix J, Figure 4 shows the c-Chart of constipation identification based on MOM PRN given pre- and post-implementation. Pre-implementation (weeks 1-25) showed an average of 3.75 instances of MOM prn given, with an upper control limit of 9.6 and a lower limit of zero. After week 25, special cause variation is demonstrated with >8 points above the center line (CL); therefore, the control limits were revised to show the new average of 11.1 with an upper limit of 21 and a lower limit of three indicating a statistically significant improvement in the instances of MOM PRN given.

The use of a continuous control chart was not appropriate to analyze the significance of Lactulose PRN and Dulcolax suppository PRN use, as well as for the diagnostic KUB ordered. There were too many zeroes on the weekly surveillance data collection to draw a meaningful evaluation of their use. Instead, the frequency of lactulose PRN, suppository PRN use, and KUB-ordered pre- and post-implementation was aggregated and illustrated in Appendix J, Figure 5

Discussion

In this EBP pilot project, the PL implemented a care bundle of interventions that included an EM, the BSFS tool, and an EHR alert system incorporated into the unit workflow to improve the monitoring and management of constipation in patients taking antipsychotics. Using the Iowa Model as a guide, a pilot project was conducted in an inpatient psychiatric unit to achieve the project's purpose of early detection of constipation and preventing hospitalizations related to fecal impaction. Data were collected through a weekly review of patients' EHR and from participants' pre and post-test results. The data analysis was illustrated in a control c-chart, tables, bar plots, and graphs.

The outcomes of this project indicated that implementing the care bundle of interventions is a practical approach to the early detection and management of constipation in patients taking antipsychotics. The results also showed an increase in patients identified with constipation post-implementation. This finding is consistent with the study by Xu et al. (2021) that identified patients taking antipsychotics at high risk for constipation side effects.

Educational Module

Findings of the pre-and post-test analysis using the paired sample *t*-Test showed that mean post-test scores were significantly higher than the pre-test scores. This finding is further supported by the Chi-squared test observed and expected frequency results in Appendix I, Table 3. The result showed that the expected correct answers on the pre-test (77) were greater than the observed correct answers (64). However, on the post-test, the observed correct answers (90) exceeded the expected results (77). On the other hand, the expected incorrect answers (23) on the pretest were more than the observed incorrect answers (36), while the observed incorrect answers (10) on the post-test were less than the expected frequencies (23). This means that the Chi-

squared test showed a relationship between the pre-and post-test results and participants' correct and incorrect answers. There was an increase in the average of correct post-test answers and a decrease in the average of incorrect post-test answers. The paired t-Test and Chi-squared test results suggest that the EM portion of the care bundle of interventions effectively increased participants' knowledge regarding BSFS and its clinical implications.

Incorporation of the BSFS and the PCC Alert System

The EM in-service was essential in incorporating the BSFS tool and PCC alert system into the pilot unit workflow. Participants were able to effectively use the BSFS tool and respond with the appropriate intervention to address stool type. This appears to result from increased knowledge of the BSFS tool based on the EM. As a result, there was an increase in the identification and treatment of constipation post-implementation. The special cause variation recorded in the control c-Chart was statistically significant, which demonstrated that there was an increase in the identification of constipation and treatment four months post-implementation based on the number of MOM PRN given. A special cause variation was noted following week 25 of the data collection. During week 25 (December 27, 2022), the PL and unit champion assessed those new and existing employees who had not received the EM; despite working on the pilot unit. These employees failed to record the stool type on the PCC accordingly. To resolve the issue, the Staff Developer and PL provided a short in-service on BSFS and the BM monitoring process in the pilot unit to all untrained staff.

The PCC alert system was not consistently activating an alert to staff to follow the recommended responses when stool types 1 or 2 were recorded. Therefore, some patients were not identified as having constipation; however, due to a secondary system check through audits by PL, this system issue was addressed and corrected by IT and the D.O.N.

There were additional data collected on other laxatives given PRN. These laxatives included lactulose and Dulcolax suppositories. These laxatives were used based on ineffective MOM PRN at the healthcare provider's discretion. The use of these laxatives was difficult to evaluate since they were not frequently used as a consistent treatment compared to the MOM PRN. Finally, the decrease in diagnostic KUBs ordered by the MD/NP post-implementation detailed in Appendix J, Figure 4 implies that implementing the care bundle of interventions may have assisted in the early detection and management of constipation. However, further data collection and analysis are needed for a valid statistical conclusion.

Surprising Findings

Although there was an increase in the identification and treatment of constipation, the team found that this outcome cannot completely be attributed to the use of the BSFS tool. One surprising finding noted from the project was that some patients sought laxatives for weight loss. This was discovered because of the ongoing communication between staff and the PL during audits, which prompted the licensed staff and MD/NP to reassess for actual constipation. KUBs were ordered, which were unremarkable, showing that the patient was not constipated. Further study of this type of behavior is warranted when considering future similar EBP projects.

Recommendations

A review of PCC post-implementation showed zero hospitalizations related to fecal impaction. Prevention of hospitalization due to unresolved constipation and fecal impaction continues to be a long-term goal for the facility. Hence, the team recommended continued use of the BSFS tool and the PCC alert system to monitor and manage constipation and to add the process to the facility's policy and procedures. This recommendation aligns with the sixth step of the Iowa Model to hardwire change into the system. Additionally, unit staff should conduct a

routine audit and review of the PCC alert system to ensure accurate stool-type reporting and reestablish process change, if indicated. The Staff Developer should also provide an EM in-service for new staff onboarding for consistency of care. Further research studies should focus on actual patients' responses to using the BSFS tool, early detection of constipation, and the approaches and management of their AIC.

Implications

Xu et al. (2021) found that constipation is often overlooked among those receiving antipsychotic medication in a psychiatric inpatient setting. In addition, patient self-reporting is a poor measure of early detection of constipation (Palmer et al., 2017; Palmer et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2021). This project found that the BSFS tool is an applicable and helpful tool for the early detection of constipation in the psychiatric inpatient setting. Using EM and the EHR alert system can increase the clinical staff's knowledge and awareness of constipation side effects of antipsychotics and assist the MD/NP in the early management of constipation and clinical decision-making. Further research is needed to study the effectiveness of AIC treatment options for psychiatric patients. Additionally, there is a need for more research into confounding factors like non-pharmacological causes of constipation in the psychiatric inpatient population.

Limitations

Although there was an improvement through the care bundle of interventions implemented, the pilot project had limitations, such as inaccurate patient and staff reporting of the stool type. Some staff reported confusion between stool Types 2 and 3. Another limitation was the intermittent inaccurate prompting of the PCC alert system. The PCC alert system was triggered when the Type 3 stool form was selected on the BSFS tool. Conversely, there were instances when the alert system needed to be activated when stool Types 1 and 2 were selected.

This may have led to inconsistent notification and activation of the constipation bundle recommendations.

Another limitation identified was that the team limited the EM in-service to level care staff only, excluding other key personnel who could have assisted in improving the monitoring and management of constipation. The PL was also unable to incorporate a monthly knowledge check in the electronic training system (Relias) as planned due to time constraints. Additionally, this project is applicable in the psychiatric inpatient setting and may have limited generalizability in other healthcare settings.

Conclusions

The pilot project addressed the need for enhanced monitoring and management of constipation in patients taking antipsychotics that triggered this EBP change. Consistent monitoring, screening, and engagement in preventative strategies for the early detection of constipation by clinical staff are recommended to help prevent AIC (De Hert et al., 2011; Logre et al., 2020; Nakamura & Nagamine, 2021; Every-Palmer et al., 2021; Shirazi et al., 2016; Xu et al., 2021). This recommendation supports this project's result that using a valid screening tool like the BSFS combined with the implementation of EM and the PCC alert system is a practical approach and strategy for the early detection and management of AIC. The project implemented an EBP change to prevent severe complications from unresolved constipation in patients taking antipsychotics. This change resulted in a positive outcome from integrating a care bundle of interventions to improve the quality of care and health condition of the vulnerable population served in the psychiatric inpatient setting. Following the last step of the Iowa Model, the team recommended disseminating the results to management for facility-wide implementation.

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Appendix A

Bristol Stool Scale Form:

Bristol Stool Form Scale

Type 1		Separate hard lumps, like nuts
Type 2		Sausage-shaped but lumpy
Type 3		Like a sausage but with cracks on its surface
Type 4		Like a sausage or snake, smooth and soft
Type 5		Soft blobs with clear-cut edges
Type 6		Fluffy pieces with ragged edges, a mushy stool
Type 7		Watery, no solid pieces

Constipated stool - Types 1 or 2

Diarrheal stool - Types 6 or 7

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Appendix B

The Iowa Model - Revised

The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

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Appendix C

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Appendix D

Internal Review Board Approval for Exemption

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APPROVAL NOTICE

*From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton*

October 17, 2022

**From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board**

To: PI: Arnold Franco

Application No. HSR-22-23-75

Study Title: Improving the Monitoring and Management of Constipation in Adult Patients Taking Antipsychotic Medications

Re: Initial Exempt Review

Appendix E

Letter of Support from Medical Director

May 11, 2022

To: Arnold Franco
DNP Student
School of Nursing
California State University, Fullerton

From: Deepak Rajpoot, MD
Medical Director, Royale TRC

To Whom It May Concern:

As the Medical Director of Royale TRC, I am pleased to support Mr. Arnold Franco in conducting his DNP project, titled "Improving the Monitoring and Management of Constipation in Adult Patients Taking Antipsychotic Medications."

Constipation is a common clinical problem seen in the psychiatric inpatient setting. This condition can be attributed to different factors, including side effects from antipsychotic medications, patients' decreased ability to communicate needs and problems, self-care and health awareness challenges, and the patients' higher pain threshold. Addressing the early detection and management of constipation and developing a care bundle that incorporates the Bristol Stool Form Scale and constipation management algorithm to prevent adverse consequences like fecal impaction, ileus, and small bowel obstruction is a significant undertaking that Mr. Franco will be able to accomplish here at the facility.

Upon all necessary CSUF IRB approvals/determinations, Mr. Franco will be allowed to collect data, access necessary documents/data, conduct essential interactions relevant to the project, and distribute surveys or other documents. Mr. Franco is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to this project follow the research and research-related policies at CSUF.

I look forward to working with Mr. Franco on this worthwhile project and wish him the best.

Sincerely,

Deepak Rajpoot, MD
Medical Director
Royale TRC

Appendix F

Informed Consent

Study Title: Improving the Monitoring and Management of Constipation in Adult Patients Taking Antipsychotic Medications

Protocol Number: HSR-22-23-75

**Researchers: Arnold Franco, MSN, RN, FNP-BC (DNP Student) and
Kate Bayhan, DNP, RN, CCRN (Faculty Adviser)**

You are being asked to participate in a doctoral project carried out by Arnold Franco, DNP student who is under the advisement of Dr. Kate Bayhan. This consent form explains the project and your part in it if you decide to participate in the project. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. Please ask the project leader to explain anything you don't understand. You can decide not to participate in the project at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of benefits if you decide to not take part in the project.

About the Project: This project is being conducted to improve the monitoring and management of constipation in patients taking antipsychotic medications

You are being asked to take part in this project because you provide a level of care to patients on Unit 2 and you will be receiving educational material and training on this evidenced based practice project as part of your usual work activities.

Length of Project: Taking part in this project will take about 6 months

Inclusion: You must be an employee of Royale TRC and be over 18 years of age to participate in the project.

If you take part in the project, you will be asked to:

- Receive training and educational material on the evidence-based practice project that will be implemented in Unit 2 that includes learning about the Bristol Stool Form Scale and its incorporation into the PontClickCare (PCC) EHR's bowel movement monitoring and constipation screening, and algorithm. Instructions will be provided to follow when receiving a constipation alert on PCC, and the documentation involved with the alert. The training includes a pre and post-test about monitoring and management of constipation. The training will be approximately 45-minute in length.
- Each month, you will receive a knowledge check related to the BSFS and constipation monitoring and management protocol on your monthly RELIAS training. This will be done to evaluate your progress towards the learning goal. This knowledge check will take no more than 5 minutes to complete.
- After six months, you will receive a 10-item post-test questionnaire to evaluate the learning that occurred regarding the educational material

Benefits: There is no direct benefit to you for participating in the project. However, if you take part in the project, you will acquire new learning and skills from the training module which pertain to the monitoring and management of constipation for patients taking antipsychotic medications and will help improve the quality of life for patients at Royale TRC in the future

Risks: There is no risk to participating in this project.

Confidentiality: The data for this project will be kept confidential as no names will be attached to the data collected. Participants will be given an assigned 3-digit code to track the pre and post questionnaire results. Should the project be published, no identifying information will be included. The results of this project may be published or presented at professional meetings, but the identities of all participants will remain anonymous

The data for this project will be kept for a minimum of 3 years after the completion of the project as required by California State University, Fullerton.

Costs: There will be no costs to you for taking part in this project. You will not receive money or any other form of compensation for taking part in this project.

Questions about the project: If you have questions about this project or this form, please contact the project leader: Arnold Franco at amfroDNP@CSU.fullerton.edu. If you have questions about your rights as a participant, or would like to report a concern or complaint about this project, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719, or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu

Participant Rights: Your participation in this project is completely voluntary. You may choose not to participate at any time. There will be no penalty to you if you choose to not take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions.

Signing for Consent Means:

- You understand the information given to you in this form.
- You have been able to ask the project leader questions and state any concerns.
- The researcher has responded to your questions and concerns.
- You believe you understand the project and the potential benefits and risks that are involved.

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and/or I have had the terms used in this consent form and their significance explained to me. By signing below, I agree that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this project. You will be given a copy of this signed and dated consent form for your records.

Name of Participant (please print) _____

Signature of Participant: _____ Date _____

Signature of Investigator _____ Date _____

Appendix G

Rome Foundation License Agreement to Use BSFS

CONTENT LICENSE AGREEMENT

This LICENSE AGREEMENT ("Agreement"), effective as of the date of the last signature ("Effective Date"), by and between the Rome Foundation, Inc. ("ROME" or "Licensor"), an organization with offices at 14460 Falls of Neuse Rd. Ste. 149-116 Raleigh, NC 27614, USA and Arnold Franco ("Licensee").

RECITALS

WHEREAS, ROME owns or has the right to license certain images, tables, and related ancillary materials ("Content");

WHEREAS, Licensee uses the Rome IV instruments in *Exhibit A*.

WHEREAS, Licensee desires to license Content from ROME;

WHEREAS, ROME is willing to provide Licensee with a license, pursuant to the terms and conditions of this Agreement; and

NOW THEREFORE, the parties agree as follows:

AGREEMENT

I. Grant of License.

1.1. **Grant.** Subject to the terms and conditions of this Agreement, and during the Term of this Agreement, ROME grants to Licensee a nonexclusive, non-transferable, non-assignable (except for as provided herein) license ("Licensee") to the Content described in *Exhibit A*.

ROME acknowledges that the Study may be conducted by Licensee, its affiliates and/or their contractors and agrees that the rights granted to Licensee under this Agreement will also benefit to such affiliates and contractors only to the extent necessary for the conduct of the study.

ROME acknowledges that Licensee may have to communicate the BSFS to ethics committees, Institution Review Boards or any regulatory authorities to conduct the Study and ROME hereby authorizes such communication.

Usage. The License shall be limited to the sole purpose of doing a quality improvement project to improve monitoring of constipation in adults taking antipsychotics in inpatient setting through the use of BSFS in practice and training purposes (the "Licensee Course").

10.9. **Counterpart Execution.** This Agreement may be executed by the parties on any number of separate counterparts, and all such counterparts so executed constitute one agreement binding on all the parties notwithstanding that all the parties are not signatories to the same counterpart.

10.10. **Entire Agreement.** This Agreement contains the entire agreement and understanding between the parties and may not be modified or amended except by written agreement executed by both of the parties.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, each of the parties has caused a duly authorized officer or agent to execute this Agreement as of the dates set forth below.

ROME FOUNDATION, INC.

Arnold Franco

By: Johannah Ruddy, MEd

By:

Name: Johannah Ruddy M. Ed.

Name: ARNOLD FRANCO

Title: COO

Title: NURSE PRACTITIONER

Date: December 15, 2022

Date: 11-21-22

EXHIBIT A
Description of licensed content

- **Bristol Stool Form Scale (BSFS)**

Appendix H

Pre and Post Test

Please encircle the best answer (Ten points).

1. Constipation can be defined as:
 - a. Frequent bowel movement (BM)
 - b. Less frequent BM
 - c. Difficulty passing hard stool.
 - d. Both B & C
 - e. All of the above
2. Constipation is common in the following population.
 - a. Older people
 - b. Patient taking antipsychotics.
 - c. Pregnant women
 - d. All of the above
 - e. Both A & B
3. The process by which stool is propelled along the colon by the contraction of muscle inside the colon wall is called?
 - a. Digestion
 - b. Evacuation
 - c. Peristalsis
 - d. Constriction
4. Patients taking these types of medication have increased risk for constipation.
 - a. Antipsychotics
 - b. Antibiotics
 - c. Laxatives
 - d. Placebos
5. Which Antipsychotic medication has a high propensity to cause constipation and blood disorder?
 - a. Quetiapine
 - b. Chlorpromazine
 - c. Haloperidol
 - d. Clozapine
6. This tool is used to help identify stool form that indicates the likelihood of constipation.
 - a. Rome IV Tool
 - b. Bristol Stool Form Scale (BSFS)
 - c. Constipation Chart
 - d. PCC BM Monitoring System
7. How many types of stool forms included in BSFS?
 - a. 3
 - b. 4
 - c. 7
 - d. 10
8. Types 1 & 2 of stool forms can be indications of constipation. What is the licensed staff expected action when a patient reports these types of stools on BSFS?

- a. Assess the patient.
 - b. If not urgent, refer to NP/MD for consultation.
 - c. Check MD order and give PRN.
 - d. No action is required as the patient only reported once.
 - e. All above except D
9. Types 3-4 stool forms are ideal stool because they are easy to pass.
- a. True
 - b. False
10. How can we prevent incidents of fecal impaction, hospitalization, and death in patients taking antipsychotics as a result of untreated constipation?
- a. Early identification of signs of constipation
 - b. Monitoring and accurate reporting of patients' BM
 - c. Encouraging lifestyle modification
 - d. Offer laxatives as needed.
 - e. Identify patients taking Clozaril and Olanzapine and discuss bowel movements with providers.
 - f. All of the above
 - g. All of the above except E

Appendix I
Tables for Data Analysis

Table 1*Frequency Table for Participants' Demographics*

Variable	N	%
ETHNICITY		
Filipino	27	50.94
Hispanic	15	28.30
Caucasian	1	1.89
African American	3	5.66
Vietnamese	7	13.21
AGE RANGE		
(20 – 30)	18	33.96
(30 – 40)	8	15.09
(40 – 50)	13	24.53
(50 – 60)	6	11.32
(60 – 70)	7	13.21
(70 – 80)	1	1.89
TITLE		
MHA	30	56.60
LVN	8	15.09
RN	10	18.87
LPT	5	9.43
GENDER		
M	26	49.06
F	27	50.94
WORK SHIFT		
NOC	13	24.53
AM	23	43.40
PM	17	32.08

Note. Frequency variables show 50.94% Filipino in Ethnicity, 33.96% belong in the 20-30 age range, 56.60% were MHAs, male and female participants are almost equally distributed, and majority (43%) work in AM shift.

Table 2

Two-Tailed Paired Samples t-Test for the Difference Between Pretest Scores and Post-Test Scores

Pretest Scores		Post-test Scores		<i>T</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>d</i>
<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>			
6.25	1.64	8.58	1.68	-10.31	< .001	1.42

Note. N = 53. Degrees of Freedom for the *t*-statistic = 52. *d* represents Cohen's *d*.

Table 3

Chi-Squared Test of Independence: Observed and Expected Frequencies

ANSWERS	QUESTIONNAIRE		χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
	PRETEST	POSTTEST			
CORRECT	64[77.00]	90[77.00]	19.09	1	< .001
INCORRECT	36[23.00]	10[23.00]			

Note. Values formatted as Observed [Expected]. Pretest correct answers were lower than expected while post-test correct answers were higher than expected.

Appendix J

Figures for Data Analysis

Figure 1

Distribution of Participants in Attendance by Job Title

Note. Job title of participants who attended the two EM in-service on November 29, 2022

Figure 2

The means of Pretest Scores and Post-Test Scores

Note. Bar plot of the means of participants pre & post-test scores with 95% CI error bars

Figure 3

Note. The number of patients identified with constipation based on the use of laxatives PRN four months pre- and post-implementation illustrates the increase identified constipation post-implementation.

Figure 4

Note. c-Chart of MOM PRN given in the span of 36 weeks collected from July 1, 2022, until March 14, 2023. The c-Chart shows a special cause (> 8 points above CL) to support significant improvement from process change.

Figure 5

Note. Frequency of other laxatives PRN given and diagnostic KUB ordered pre- and post-implementation (7/1/22 to 3/14/23)